

GraphQL: A Systematic Mapping Study

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GraphQL is a query language and execution engine for web application programming interfaces (APIs) proposed as an alternative to improve data access problems and versioning of representational state transfer APIs. In this article, we thoroughly study the GraphQL field, first describing the GraphQL paradigm and its conceptual framework, and then conducting a systematic mapping study of 84 primary studies selected from an original set of 3,185. Our work analyzes trends or knowledge gaps about GraphQL by general classification of the studies and specific classification of this research topic. The study's main conclusions show that GraphQL adoption is growing in the community as a strong alternative to implement APIs. However, we identified the need to strengthen the amount and rigor of empirical evidence collection in applied industry and government studies. In addition, we revealed the opportunity for specific studies on most GraphQL components, especially the consumption of GraphQL API services.

CCS Concepts: • **Applied computing** → **Service-oriented architectures**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Software as a service orchestration system**; **API languages**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Cloud computing**; • **Information systems** → **RESTful web services**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: GraphQL, API, microservices, systematic mapping study

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1 INTRODUCTION

Today, **Software-as-a-Service (SaaS)** has received significant attention as one of the three main service models of cloud computing (i.e., **Platform-as-a-Service or (PaaS)** and **Infrastructure-as-a-Service or (IaaS)** [33, 54]). SaaS utilizes the internet to deliver applications to its users, which are managed by a provider. Therefore, selecting the best SaaS provider among those available is

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